

Stim Objects Survey Questions

Screening & Eligibility

To be eligible to participate in this study, answers must be "Yes" to the following "Yes/No" questions.

Are you at least 18 years old?

- Yes
- No

Do you identify as autistic?

- Yes
- No

Do you stim?

To stim includes self-stimulating behaviors or actions—for example, hand-manipulation of a textured object, stroking hair, or other repetitive body motions—that often provide benefits to autistic people such as comfort, distraction, enjoyment, or relief from over-stimulation.

- Yes
- No

Do you live in the United States and have a U.S. street address (non-P.O. box) that we can mail stim objects to?

- Yes
- No

Are you allergic to any materials commonly found in fabrics (such as acrylic, nylon, elastane, polyester, wool, cotton, linen, etc.)? If so, please list them below so we can confirm that none of the objects contain them when determining your eligibility.

- No
- Yes (please list the materials you are allergic to)

Survey

What gender do you identify with and what are your preferred pronouns?

At what age did you first suspect you are autistic, or receive a diagnosis (if applicable)?

- Under 4

- 4 - 9
- 10 - 19
- 20 - 29
- 30 - 39
- 40 - 49
- 50 - 59
- 60 - 69
- 70 - 79
- 80 or older

What is your perspective on stimming? (e.g., do you enjoy doing it, view it positively or negatively, etc.)

In which situations do you find stimming most helpful?

Please list any actions, behaviors, and/or objects you typically use to stim.

Have you encountered stigmas around stimming or ever been told not to stim?

- Yes
- No
- Maybe (not sure)

[if answered yes to encountered stigmas] In what situations have you experienced stigmas around stimming? (e.g., school, therapies such as ABA, work, home, etc.)

[if answered yes to encountered stigmas] Has this impacted your view of stimming or how often you stim?

How do you experience each of the sensory stimuli listed below? Please choose from the following options for each.

Unremarkable (meaning the stimulus does not impact you in a significant way)

Hypo-sensitive (meaning you are under-sensitive to the stimulus, e.g., you may not notice when you are injured if you are hypo-sensitive to touch)

Hyper-sensitive (meaning you are over-sensitive to the stimulus, e.g., you may experience pain in response to loud noises or have intense reactions to music if you are hyper-sensitive to sound)

Situational (meaning your sensitivity is varied depending on the particular circumstance, e.g., you might feel pain from loud mechanical noises but don't easily notice people's voices)

	Column Options ▾				Column Options ▾
	Response				Optionally, describe your response.
	Unremarkable	Hypo-sensitive	Hyper-sensitive	Situational	Description
Touch/Texture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
Sound	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
Sight/Visuals	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
Smell	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>

Please describe experiences/reactions you have had interacting with fabrics, clothing, and textured materials.

How important is it to you that a stim object is discrete/doesn't draw attention to you when you are stimming around others?

- Not at all important
- Slightly important
- Moderately important
- Very important
- Extremely important

Optionally, describe your response.